

Human Rights Violation amidst IPOB Crisis in Anambra State: An in-depth Analysis

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Abstract: This research work is on the human rights violation amidst the IPOB crisis in Anambra State: an in-depth analysis. For some years now, Anambra State has been besieged by the separatist group called Independent People of Biafra (IPOB). The group's activities have been characterized by disturbances to the peace and order of Anambra State, with the attendant violation of human rights such as civil, political, economic, and social rights. The government and its security agents are not left out in the same violations of human rights. The objectives of the research are to investigate the perceived incidences of human rights violations, the causes of the violations of human rights in Anambra State, the extent to which violations of human rights affect the citizens, and to recommend the egalitarian strategy such as observance of rule of law in the management of violation of human rights associated with the IPOB agitation. The violations of human rights manifest in the restriction of movement imposed by IPOB, destruction of lives and properties, vandalization of the government's infrastructure, and destabilization of the political system, all by IPOB. The research is anchored on the Interest Theory of Rights, Marxism, and Feminism. The theories synchronize and deal with the basic rights and freedoms of human beings. The research is significant as it will provide policy guidelines to the government in terms of the management of the IPOB crisis-prone agitation. The researchers recommend, among others, good leadership and strong institutions that have the potential to quell agitations.

Keywords: Anambra State, Crisis, Human Rights, IPOB, Violation, Agitation.

Introduction

The problems of the violation of human rights in the world today worry all and sundry, especially when it is associated with agitations. It poses a great challenge to the government, non-governmental

organizations as well as traditional and religious institutions and their leaders. Respect for human rights essentially constitutes a yardstick for assessing any government's great ethical concerns. It also measures the extent to which

religious adherents practice the teachings of their respective religions.

In Nigeria, especially in the crisis-prone southeastern state of Anambra, violation of human rights is a serious problem. Today, in Nigeria and Anambra State, citizens do not sleep with their eyes closed not primarily because of hunger and poverty, although they are inclusive, because of prevailing insecurity within which human rights are violated and abused.

Unfortunately, the proliferation of light arms and ammunition, a secessionist bid of a group (Independent People of Biafra, IPOB), unprofessional conduct of some armed security personnel, and perceived bad leadership have worsened the violation of human rights, consciously or inadvertently. The reason for all this is perhaps owed to the observation of Akhain and Chizea (2011) that “contrary to democratic ethos, the state [Nigeria] is still largely authoritarian in leadership and security operations”. The government’s and its security agents’ manhunt, arrest, and prolonged detention of human rights activists and campaigners of ethnic determination but perceived as enemies significantly fuel the abuse and violation of human rights. For instance, the arrest and detention of Sunday Adeyemo (alias

Sunday Igboho), Omoyele Sowore and Nnamdi Kanu compelled their followers to take laws into their own hands.

To date, the rampant killings of innocent citizens, consistent attacks and violent death of security agents such as police and soldiers, destruction of lives and properties, and the illegal sit-at-home orders and curfews perpetrated by Eastern Security Networks (ESN) in Anambra are attributed to the continued detention of Nnamdi Kanu, even after Nigerian court of competent jurisdiction has acquitted and discharged him. Aside from the brutality of the police on Nigerian youths and the corresponding #EndSARS protest that still reechoes in our minds, Nwangwu (2022) contends that “state repression accounts for the mutation of the separatist strategies of the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) from non-violence to armed struggle”.

As a grave and life-threatening problem, the violation of human rights in Anambra state requires a critical, feasible, and egalitarian solution, especially from the academia. It is only thorough and rigorous research that can bring to bare the remote and immediate causes, the consequential effects, the real victims, and informed recommendations. Thus, the reasons and objectives of this research.

The Concept of Human Rights

Human rights are a compound concept popular to many people in contemporary society. The concept traces its origin to the declaration of a Persian King, Cyrus the Great, in 539 BC that all human beings had the right to choose their religion and established social equality (Moyn, 2010). Other documents that support the concept of human rights include the Magna Carta (1212), The Petition of Rights (1628), the US Constitution (1767), the French Declaration of Rights of the Right of Man and the Citizen (1789), the US Bill of Rights (1791), the United Nation Charter (1945) and finally the summit of all declarations, Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948). All these documents are targeted at global mobilization towards confronting injustice, inhumanity, oppression, and other forms of unfairness or simply violating human rights.

Human rights are inalienable fundamental rights to which every human being is naturally endowed. The rights are rudimentarily inherent to all human beings irrespective of their nationality, place of birth, residence, sex, national or ethnic lineage, religion, colour, language, and social or political status. Hannum (2006) states that “the inalienable rights are universal (applicable everywhere),

inalienable (they should not be taken away except in special situations and according to due process), egalitarian (the same everywhere), indivisible, equal and non-discriminatory”. Human rights embody a universal value that applies to all individuals no matter their cultural lineage, the place, and the circumstances of their birth. Adetoro and Olugbenga (2014) see human rights as “legal entitlements which every citizen could enjoy without fear of government or its fellow citizens”. For Kaluge (2013),

Human rights are those rights that cannot be said to have been given to man by man but are earned by man for being a human being because these are necessary for his continuous happy existence with himself, and his fellow man, and for participation in a complex society.

As norms, “human rights aspire to protect all people everywhere from severe political, legal, and social abuses” (Nickel,

2021). Aduba (2012) sees human rights as “those rights that are in the very nature of human person.... Human rights are rights possessed by all persons by their common humanity to live a life of freedom and dignity”. In a nutshell, and according to the United Nations Equality and Human Rights Commission (2023), human rights are “the basic rights and freedoms that belong to every person in the world, from birth until death”. United Nations Equality and Human Rights Commission (2023) gives us the four basic features of human rights as follows: (a) They apply regardless of where you are from, what you believe, or how you choose to live your life; (b) They can never be taken away, although they can sometimes be restricted; (c) These basic rights are based on shared values like dignity, fairness, equality, respect and independence; and (d) These values are defined and protected by law. Institutions and individuals are also under obligation to safeguard, boost, and sustain human rights in words, actions, and deeds.

The basic characteristics of human rights are that they “are regularly protected in municipal and international law and applicable everywhere and at every time in the sense of being universal” (Nickel, 2021); inalienable and egalitarian in the sense that they cannot be taken away

from anybody except in special situations and according to due process and being same for everyone (Hannum, 2006; UN, 2014); requiring empathy and the rule of law (Bass, 2010). They addressed the questions about the existence, content, nature, universality, justification, and legal status of human rights.

The Concept of Violation of Human Rights

Violation is the noun form of the verb, *violate*, which means “to go against or refuse to obey a law, an agreement” (Hornby, 2006). Violation as a concept is synonymous with desecration, infringement, and intrusion. Violation of human rights is the systematic process of infringing and desecrating the codes, ethics, and contents of human rights. Schwie (2023) conceptualizes human rights violation as “the disallowance of the freedom of thought and movement to which all humans legally have right”. Maiese (2003) asserts that “to violate the most basic rights... is to deny individuals their fundamental moral entitlements”. It is, in essence, “to treat human beings as if they are less than human and undeserving of respect and dignity” (Maiese, 2003).

The perceived Incidences of Human Right Violation

The incidences of human rights violations abound in Nigeria at large and Anambra State in particular. There is hardly any form of fundamental human rights that is not periodically violated in Nigeria. The worrisome aspect is the impunity and gravity with which they occur as well as the preponderance of their occurrences. The relative incidences of violation of rights are not limited to Nigeria and the crisis-prone eastern state of Anambra. They also have a global perspective. From the global perspective, Maiese (2003) states that “some of the gravest violations of the rights to life are massacres, the starvation of the entire population and genocide... killing group members, causing them serious bodily or mental harm, imposing measures to prevent birth, or forcibly transferring children”. Others crimes against humanity such as torture, slavery, rape, forced and (or) enforced sterilization or medical experimentation, constitute a violation of human rights. “War crimes by any individual whether military or civilian, taking hostages, firing on localities that are undefended and without military significance, such as schools or hospitals, inhuman treatment of prisoner, including biological experiment and pillage or purposeless destruction of

property” (Paust et al, 2001), “the use of weapons that cause unnecessary suffering or long-term environmental damage” (Hubert and Weise, 2001) comprise a violation of human rights. Other conspicuous but regrettable incidences of violation of human rights include sexual violence and assault (sexual mutilation, sexual humiliation and forced pregnancy), especially during armed conflict and trafficking in women as a form of sexual slavery (UN, 2021), a program of torture by the government (physical or psychological) (Cassese, 1990), forced disappearance and secret killing and burial (UN, 2000), “... acts typically deemed crimes against humanity such as genocide, torture, slavery, rape, and deliberate starvation” (Nzarga, 2014).

The Causes of the Violation of Human Rights in Nigeria

The Nigerian experiences have indeed shown the level at which citizens’ integrity, self-worth, and dignity are not respected and protected. Most cases of the violation of human rights are traceable to these generative forces. Several factors account for the violation of human rights. Weston (2023) observes, first and foremost, painful frustration by social as well as natural forces that breed and nurture violations of human rights. Such

forces result in “exploitation, oppression, persecution, and other forms of deprivation” (Weston, 2023). The “degradation and violation of women” (Bunch, 2006) which occur in the forms of “domestic violence, reproductive choice, and trafficking of women and girls for sex work” (Okin, 1998) are tangentially linked to social and natural forces, and they “often occur in the home at the hands of other family members and ... in the private sphere” (Nickel, 2021). It is important to note that “one of the main purposes of including social rights in human rights documents and treaties was to promote serious efforts to combat poverty, lack of education, and unhealthy living conditions” (Langford, 2013). Thus, poverty, illiteracy, and insalubrious living conditions can wittingly or inadvertently compel one to give in to the violation of his/her rights.

Basically, violations of human rights are seen to occur when the government fails in its statutory responsibility of protecting vulnerable people and groups. The government is expected to protect its citizens through its organs and security agencies such as the judiciary, police, army, and other paramilitary agents. Thus, institutional corruption, lack of independence of the judiciary, political interference, and democratic deficit

contribute immensely to the violation of human rights in Nigeria. Instead of protection, we rather often see violations of citizens’ rights such as civil rights which include the right to life, safety, and equality before the law, and political rights which include the right to a fair trial and the right to vote. It is important that “serious difficulties arise ... when those in power are responsible for human rights violations” (Maiese, 2003). It is even more worrisome that “the efforts of the National Human Rights Commission to halt the infringements of human rights of citizens are usually ignored by security forces” (Falana, 2021). Distressingly perturbing is the Nigerian federal government’s “endorsement of official impunity by insisting that national security supersedes the rule of law under the Buhari administration” (Falana, 2021). With this perspective, the Federal Government of Nigeria and its agencies cannot but “refuse to comply with over 100 judgments delivered by municipal courts in favour of victims of human rights” (Falana, 2021). Other rights that are violated which often attract reprisal and further violation of human rights are moral, economic, social, cultural, and solidarity or community rights (Adetoro and Olugbenga 2014). Maiese (2003) insists that

Violations of political
and economic rights

are the root causes of many crises. When rights to adequate food, housing, employment, and cultural life are denied, and large groups of people are excluded from society's decision-making processes, there is likely to be great social unrest. Such conditions often give rise to justice conflicts, in which parties demand that their basic needs be met.

Cassese (1990) adds that the causes of human rights violations “have to do with underdevelopment, economic pressure, various social problems, and international issues”. All of these rights are violated through “intimidation, undemocratic imposition of candidates for political offices, assassination and the huge finances on prebendal political environment” (Akhaine and Chizea, 2011); “corruption, bribery and nepotism, deprivation of the right to safe, clean and healthy environment” (Adetoro and Olugbenga, 2014); “trafficking circumstances” (Awah, 2009); “neglect, harm, abuse, exploitation and deprivation of orphans and vulnerable children” (Danladi, 2009).

Protracted conflict is a veritable factor that propels the violation of human rights. Prolonged dispute engenders war crimes, genocide, and other crimes against humanity. Maiese (2003) writes that “many conflicts are sparked or spread by violation of human rights. For instance, massacres or torture may inflame hatred and strengthen an adversary's determination to continue fighting. Violations may also lead to further violence from the other side and can contribute to a conflict's spiraling out of control”. Kennedy (2001) adds that “human rights abuses are often at the center of wars...”. It is aphoristically evident that there is an integrality between human right abuses and protracted conflict. In fact, “abuse of human rights often leads to conflict, and conflict typically results in human rights violations” (Maiese, 2003). The impunity of Nigeria's security agencies, especially the police and the army, has been adduced as one of the fundamental causes of violation of human rights. Nzarga (2014) unequivocally states that “... Nigerian security services have been accused of being one of the greatest violators of the ... rights in Nigeria”. In the same vein, “numerous Nigerians had long accused the controversial police unit (SARS) of committing acts of extortion, rape, torture and murder” (Dark, 2020).

Examples of police brutality, rape, extortion, and murder abound. We would mention just a few here. On 5 January 2020, three Nigerian police force officers were arrested for beating a bus passenger, Justice Obasi, for refusing to unlock his mobile phone (Channels Television, 2020). Abiola (2020) reports a similar arrest of police officers for beating a woman at the Odo Ori Market in Iwo, Osun State. Agyeman (2020) reports a Nigerian police officer who was arrested for assaulting a port worker. On 2 August 2019 (AfricaNews, 2019), and 28 April 2020 (The Port City News, 2020), there are cases of police officers murdering a man during a raid in Lagos and shooting to death a female police officer by his colleagues in River State. Sahara Reporters of 31 July 2020 tells us of the arrest of Insp. Peter Eba was arrested for raping a woman at a checkpoint while Obaji (2020) narrates how police officers in Abuja raped some of the 65 women who were arrested for illicit nightclub activity. All these and many more provoked the EndSARS bloody and damning nationwide protest. Thus, on 22 October 2020, the erstwhile Nigerian president, Muhammadu Buhari, publicly disbanded and dismantled the Special Anti-Robbery Squad (SARS).

In the same vein, the Nigerian soldiers have, in one way, or the other, through professional misconduct, necessitated a violation of human rights. For instance, Amnesty International (2020) reveals that in March “some Nigerian army soldiers took advantage of food shortages at refugee camps in Bornu State and raped women at female-designated ‘satellite camps’ in exchange for granting them food”. On 4 April 2020, BBC News Pidgin reports that three army soldiers were arrested in Lagos State for issuing threats to rape women. All these and many more have attracted either outright public condemnation, the outcry by those whose rights are violated, reprisal attacks on the soldiers, or distrust of the soldiers as well as their attendant further violation of human rights.

The Causes of the Violation of Human Rights in Anambra State

Anambra is the prototype state of our investigation in Nigeria. Chapter IV of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 as amended lists out fundamental human rights to be enjoyed by all the citizens of the country; among which are the right to life, right to dignity of the human person, right to freedom from discrimination, right to private and family life, right to fair hearing, right to personal liberty, etc. The rights are

consolidated by National Ethics. Chapter II, article 23 gives us the ethics as discipline, integrity, the dignity of labour, social justice, religious tolerance, self-reliance, and patriotism. Unfortunately, none of these laws and, even the national ethics, have been disincentive and deterrent to the violators of human rights in Nigeria at large and in Anambra in particular.

In Anambra State, human rights violations are caused by the government, security agents, and non-uniform individuals. Nwanguma (2013) laments three areas in which Mr. Peter Obi's attitude and governance style facilitated the violation of human rights, threatened public safety, and subverted due process and the rule of law. These areas include the government's failure to effectively investigate and disclose the outrageous sudden discovery of several floating human corpses in Ezu River in Anambra State; arbitrary ordering and personal supervision of the demolition of properties of people accused of crime in the state; and the use of Special Anti-Robbery Squad (SARS) in committing illegalities in the state. For Nwanguma (2013), these government dispositions are antidemocratic; impede public safety, security, and justice; obturate due process and legality; and violate human rights and dignity. Ajayi (2020), a reporter with the

International Center for Investigative Reporting (ICIR), asserts emphatically that "Anambra Police Command is notorious for the rights violation of citizens. Despite efforts of the police authorities to enforce discipline and ethical conduct among the rank and file, many of them continue to abuse the rights of Nigerians without recourse to laws and police rules". Ajayi (2020) gives an example of the gruesome murder of 22-year-old Ebuka Nwoye on 15 April 2020 by a trigger-happy SARS police team that was enforcing the COVID-19 lockdown. Another grievous violation of human rights was the extortion of a whopping six million naira from Ugochukwu Oraefo, a businessman, by Awkuzu SARS in Anambra State. Ugochukwu's only crime was that he gave kidnappers money for threatening him without reporting to the police. So, he was arrested, threatened with death, and detained and six million naira was paid for his release (Ajayi, 2020). Other human rights abuses in Anambra State by the police include "extorting money brazenly from keke riders and those riding small trucks..., unlawful arrest, prolonged detention, torture and all forms of degradation of human rights" (Ajayi, 2020). Amnesty International (2020) reports the severe traumatization of one Mr. Miracle after his

arrest and detention in a starvation cell for about forty days without food and water at Neni SARS in Anambra.

In Anambra State, human rights abuses are not only carried out by security agents but also by individual citizens. Ajayi (2020) quotes Okechukwu Okite, a human right lawyer as sharing his experience during his investigation.

In Anambra State, some people derive joy in violating other people's rights, intimidating them, and abusing the law with impunity. They sometimes misinform the police and use them to intimidate fellow citizens. In some cases, it goes beyond unlawful arrests as such persons are detained without trial. During the lockdown, we received several complaints of domestic violence, child abuse, and sexual assaults...

In fact, "one of the commonest abuses of human rights witnessed in the area (Anambra) is gender-based Violence, GBV, which has seen women and girls harassed and exploited by the male folks" (Ajayi, 2020). For instance, Onyeka Onyeocha from Nibo was severally physically assaulted, amidst threat to life, his mother, Mrs. Onyeocha Diana, threw

her belongings out, destroyed some of her property, and finally ejected her from their family house (Ajayi, 2020).

The unknown gunmen's attacks on the police, soldiers, and government facilities constitute a very serious violation of human rights. During the attacks, lives are lost, properties are destroyed and citizens' movements are highly restricted. The emergence of unknown gunmen in Anambra, and in other southeastern states, is the aftermath of police brutality, government insensitivity to the plight of the people or poor governance, and political wrangling among the opposing parties.

In Anambra state, for instance, on 24 February 2021, at Ekwulobia, one police officer was killed and a patrol vehicle was burnt (Yusuf, 2021), and on 18 March 2021, at Okacha Junction in Neni, a police officer was killed while others sustained gunshot injuries (Ukpong, 2021). In the same vein, on 27 April 2021, at a Naval checkpoint along the Onitsha-Owerri highway, one naval personnel was killed and two others were seriously injured (Daka et al, 2021). These kinds of attacks and killings have continued to date.

In a nutshell, Anambra State has been witnessing and still experiences unprecedented violations of human rights.

According to Ajayi (2020), “in 2018, the National Human Rights Commission (NHRC) in Anambra State documented 110 complaints on human rights abuse....” In 2019, NHRC received 195 complaints ..., 36 bothered on rape as well as domestic, sexual and gender-based violence.

The Effects of Human Rights Violations in Anambra State

The depressing consequences of the violations of human rights on the individuals (citizens), families, society, and the government are devastatingly tremendous. The elementary essence of the institution and constitutionalization of human rights is to ensure human beings' individual and collective well-being as well as ascertain and ensure communal, national, and international peace, harmony, progress, and stability in all ramifications. Unfortunately, these noble and positively result-oriented objectives are often thwarted by the violation of the said human rights. In Nigeria in general and Anambra State in particular (and as obtains in the other parts of the world), “human rights violations and abuses have held our people down, devaluing our cherished values and constituting blight on our diplomatic relations with the rest of the world” (Adetoro and Olugbenga, 2014). Weston (2023) categorically states

that violation of human rights results in “exploitation, oppression, persecution, and other forms of deprivations”. Adetoro and Olugbenga (2014) itemizes the various aftermaths of abuses of human rights in Nigeria:

Human rights abuses ... often lead to poverty which is so prevalent due to massive abuse of public funds. This is a result of a high rate of unemployment which has resulted in youth's involvement in crimes such as robbery, internet scams, and kidnapping for survival. Secondly, human rights abuse has obvious hindrances to national development. Thirdly, it also breeds a high insecurity rate as a protection of lives and properties as witnessed under conflicts in the Niger Delta region and the various ethno-religious violence. Equally, the poor health care facilities and diseases are a result of the government's non-challant attitude to the well-being of the citizens. Human rights abuse has created unlawful detention and lawlessness with gross violation of the rule of law. Furthermore, human rights abuses make people unpatriotic as many Nigerians are not proud of calling Nigeria their fatherland.

Protracted conflict and warfare and their resultant genocide are the direct consequences of perceived and evidential signs of violation of human rights. Collateral, tremendous suffering and devastation, massacres, death, and starvation are associated with protracted conflict and warfare. Genocide summarizes all the above. Maiese (2003) sees genocide as “an international extermination of a single ethnic, racial, or religious group”. In addition, “killing group members, causing them serious bodily or mental harm, imposing measures to prevent birth, or forcibly transferring children are all ways to bring about the destruction of a group” (Maiese, 2003) and they are immediate and remote aftermaths of violation of human rights. Beneath warfare is an internal conflict that arises out of identity crises/issues (Kennedy, 2001). With internal conflict “the ‘outsider’ is dehumanized, making human rights violations such as severe discrimination or ethnic cleansing all the more psychologically feasible” (Kennedy, 2001). Also, during armed conflict, sexual assaults in the form of sexual mutilation, sexual humiliation, and forced pregnancy are prevalent. Maiese (2003) observes that the above crimes during the war are “motivated in part by long-held view that women are the ‘spoils’ of war to which

soldiers are entitled”. Protracted conflict and war are also disadvantageous characteristics of forced disappearance. United Nations (2000) documents that “tens of thousands of people detained in connection with conflicts disappear each year, and are usually killed and buried in secrets”. Human Rights Watch (2001) regrets that “corpses of those killed are buried in unmarked graves or left at dumpsite in an attempt to conceal acts of torture and summary execution...”. More traditionally regrettable is that “because people disappear without any trace, families do not know whether their loved ones are alive or dead” (Maiese, 2003).

The illegal sit-at-home curfew/order every Monday (and lately weeks or months) by IPOB to protest the continued incarceration and trial of Nnamdi Kalu has far-reaching negative effects. The enforcement of the sit-at-home and the substantial compliance restrict people from their right to free movement; necessitate the closure of schools (primary, secondary, and tertiary); and inevitably halt socio-economic activities. Many times, during the enforcement of the sit-at-home, somewhat stubborn people who violate the order are killed while the excessive militarized responses by the government security forces result in loss of lives and properties. For example, in

the protest of the Buhari government's prolonged detention of Nnamdi Kalu, IPOB on Sunday in Anambra State, killed "a woman, her 4 kids and 6 other northerners" (Eleweke et al, 2022). Also, Eze, Uzoaro, and Ndukwu (2021) state that "since February 2021, a series of deadly attacks have been launched on security formations in Anambra in Aguata and Orumba North Local Government Areas respectively, leading to the death of 16 policemen and 4 naval officers". Today, in Onitsha and Nnewi, the business hubs of Anambra state and her neighbouring states, businesses, religious, social, and academic activities are grounded. Awka, the capital city is not left out of the imbroglio of restriction of movement. In fact, at a time, the state government has to move the Monday school day to Saturday in honour of the sit-at-home order by IPOB.

Conclusion

Violation of human rights is no doubt a global problem but it seems to take a prevalent proportion in the African continent. The insurgency in the northeast and west, farmer-herder clash and cattle rustling in the north-central, kidnapping and militancy in the south-south and currently in Abuja, the capital territory, and IPOB/ESN insurgency in the southeast have continued to threaten the

very foundation of Nigeria's unity in diversity and economic stability.

The Anambra case vis-à-vis the violation of human rights seems hydra-headed as it is contextualized within the separatist agitation for independence. The battle between IPOB/ESN and the security agents on the one hand, and the state governments of the southeast on the other hand, makes the violation of human rights more complicated to comprehend. In the state of Anambra, it is decipherable from the responses of the questionnaire respondents that both the IPOB/ESN, the security agents, and the government are guilty of the violation of human rights; the reason being that each group claims absolute right of forceful execution of political rights and will. The consequences of this power tussle are the repression of peace and order, and the attendant violation of fundamental human rights.

Finally, Ajayi (2020) points out with particular reference to Anambra that "... Nigerians have attributed the increasing spate of human rights violations/abuses to poverty, ignorance, cultural and traditional inhibitions, fear of being hunted by violators, as well as general lack of interest in pursuing reported cases to a logical conclusion". The contribution of this study is bringing to the fore the realities of the violation of human rights

associated with IPOB agitations. It also provides policy guidelines in terms of the management of the IPOB crisis-prone agitations. The critical investigation of the perceived incidences of human rights violations; the degree to which citizens are exposed to the violation; the effects of the violations on the individuals, family members, and society; and the causes of the violations in Anambra State is expected to enkindle in other researchers the zeal to investigate other states for comparative analysis.

Recommendations

1. Good leadership and a strong institution are classically important. Good leadership entails understanding the pulse and needs of the citizens and attending to them as and when due. Insensitive leadership brings about protest and revolution. Even the purported and proposed peaceful protest can degenerate into a violent and crimson one with its resultant violation of human rights. A strong institution is a function and manifestation of good leadership. It makes governance easy and result-oriented. With good leadership characterized by exemplary disposition and strong institutions, violations of human rights would be highly minimized.

2. Leadership and citizenship value reorientation is greatly recommended. Value reorientation has the potential to

make people turn a new leaf. It sharpens the sense of discernment and instills the right perception, collective tolerance, and corporate understanding. It makes for good leadership and fruitful followership. Buhari's WAI, Babangida's MAMSER, Abacha's WAI-C, Goodluck Jonathan's Rebranding, and lately Buhari's Change Agenda were reorientation programs that had positive impacts on people. The National Orientation Agency (NOA) should reenact these programs and devise strategies for incorporating Reorientation in the school curriculum.

3. There should be sustained sensitization of Nigerians on the need to report human rights violations to the National Human Commission (NHC) or the police, and (or) seek redress in the competent court of jurisdiction. The report should be treated with absolute confidentiality and immediacy while the court should deliver sound judgment so that justice should not be denied in the course of unnecessary delay. Quick dispensation of justice would certainly deter prospective and potential violators.

4. Quality training and retraining of security agents must be prioritized by the government. Modern security practices require a more intelligent, kinetic, and non-kinetic approach to many complex

crisis situations. Security practice has gone beyond merely carrying guns, intimidation, and shooting at random. It has also gone beyond unwarranted vengeance and revenge as we often see from the Nigerian army and police. Examples of such training include crisis intervention, use of force and de-escalation techniques, emergency operation procedure, technical security, security management, and compliance training. Granted, the death of a soldier or policeman is a monumental loss to the family, other dependants, and the nation, yet, it does not warrant unnecessary burning of innocent peoples' houses, shops and massive retaliatory killings of passers-by or undue punishment of the motoring public and travelers. The arsonists (or unknown gunmen) and terrorists can be identified and sought out with intelligence and non-kinetic means without the right of movements of citizens being disrupted as well as destruction of their hard-earned properties. All these can be achieved via advanced retraining of security agents.

5. It is imperative for security agents to show civility in their relationship with the citizenry. The overzealousness and transfer of aggression by the security agents are not necessary in the execution of their statutory security work. They

ought to be guided by renewed objectivity. The cliché, “police is your friend”, should be seen in the practice of their conduct rather than mere slogans. Friendship is characterized by love, civility, tolerance, and understanding. Civility embodies perfunctory politeness and showing regard for others. Thus, every security agent should imbibe the virtue and culture of civility. With civility, inculcated through police and army reforms, the personnel would see the need to respect the fundamental rights of the citizens at all times. The police authorities should, therefore, devise an accountability mechanism to ensure that civility is not just encouraged but enforced.

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References

- Abiola, R. (2020). Lockdown: 2 police officers on camera assaulting a woman in Osun arrested. <https://www.igit.ng/nigeria-news>. Retrieved October 15, 2023.
- Adetoro, R. A. and Olugbenga, O. M. (2014). Challenges of human rights abuses in Nigerian democratic governance - which way forward? *Journal of Social Economics Research*. 1(5), 87-96.
- Aduba, J. N. (2012). Inquiries of human rights practice in Nigeria: Past, present and future. *54th University of Jos Inaugural Lecture Series*.
- Africa News. (2019). Nigeria policemen arrested for murder after #stop police killing protest. <https://www.africanew/2019/04/02-nigerian-policemen-arrested-for-murder>. Retrieved October 20, 2023.
- Agymen, A. (2020). Coronavirus lockdown: Nigerian police officer arrested for assaulting civilian. <https://www.adomonline.com>. Retrieved October 21, 2023.
- Ajayi, A. (2020). In Anambra, police violate the rights of Nigerians with impunity, and people are helpless. *International Center for Investigative Journalism (ICIR)*. <https://www.icirnigeria.org/in-anambra-police-violate-rights-of-nigerians-with-impunity-and-people-are-helpless>. Retrieved October 10, 2023.
- Akhaine, S. O. and Chizea, B. U. (2011). State of human rights in Nigeria. *CENCOD Annual Report*. Center for Constitutionalism and Demilitarization, 51-16.
- Amnesty International. (2020). Nigeria's starving women were raped by soldiers and militia who claim to be rescuing them. <https://www.amnesty.org>. Retrieved October 10, 2023.
- Awah, I. M. (2009). Human rights violation: A perceptive on women trafficking. *Nigerian Journal of Social Studies*. 12 (2), 256-164.
- Bass, G. J. (2010). Samuel Moyn: The old new thing. *The new republic*. <https://www.trn.com/article/books-and-arts/magazine/78542/the-old-new-thing-human-right?> Retrieved July 10, 2023.
- BBC News Pidgin. (2020). Army arrests soldiers wey threaten to rape women. <https://www.bbc.com/pidgin>. Retrieved October 15, 2023.
- Beitz, C. (2009). *The Idea of Human Rights*. Oxford University Press.
- Bunch, C. (2006). Women's rights as human rights. B. Lockwood (ed.) *Women's Rights: A Human Rights Quarterly Reader*. John Hopkins University Press, 56-62.
- Cassese, A. (1990). *Human Rights in a Changing World*. Temple University Press.
- Channels Television. (2020). VIRAL VIDEO: police officer arrested after beating up bus passenger: Confiscating his phone in Enugu. <https://www.chsnnelstv.com/2020/01/05-police-arrest-three-officers-for-assaulting-man-in-Enugu>. Retrieved September 10, 2023.
- Daka, T., Abuh, A., Udejah, G., Osuji, C., Uzoma, N., and Jegede, A. (2021).. Again, unknown gunmen raze Abia police station, and kill two cops in A'ibom. *The Guardian*. <https://www.guardian.ng/news/again-unknown-gunmen-raze-abia-police-kill-two-cops-in-aibom>. Retrieved November 17, 2023.

- Danladi, N. E. (2009). Care of orphans and the vulnerable children in Nigeria: The social responsibility for all. *Nigerian Journal of Social Studies*. 12 (2), 130-141.
- Dark, S. (2020). #EndSARS: How Nigerians harness social media against police abuse. <https://www.adjazeera.com>. Retrieved August 10, 2023.
- Eleweke, T., Dalibi, A., Isamotu, I. and Liman, D. (2022). IPOB kills a woman, 4 kids, 6 other northerners in Anambra. *Daily Trust*. <https://www.dailytrust.com/ipob-kills-woman-4-kids-6-other-northerners-in-anambra>. Retrieved November 9, 2023.
- Eze, M; Uzoaro, S. and Ndukwu, O. (2021). Who's burning South-East, South-South? *The Sun Newspaper*. <https://www.sunnewsonline.com/whos-burning-south-east-south-south>. Retrieved November 15, 2023.
- Falana, F. (2021). Why abuse of human rights has continued unabated in Nigeria. *Premium Times*. <https://www.premuimtimesng.com/opinion/500654/why-human-rights-abuse-has-continued-unabated-in-nigeria-ny-femi-falana.html>. Retrieved August 15, 2023.
- Hannum, H. (2006). The concept of human rights. *International Human Rights: Problems of Law, Policy and Practice*. Aspen Publishers, 112-123.
- Hornby, A. S. (2006). *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary*. 7th ed. Oxford University Press.
- Hubert, D and Weiss, T.G. (2001). *The Responsibility to the Project: Supplementary Volume to the Report of International Commission on Intervention and State Sovereignty*. International development Research Centre.
- Human Rights Watch. (2001). Dirty war in Chechnya: Forced disappearance, torture, and summary execution. <https://www.hrw.org/report/2001/chechnya/RSCH0301.pdf>. Retrieved December 6, 2023.
- Kaluge, D. (2013). Human rights abuses. <https://www.davidkatuge.hubpages.com/hub/human-rights-abuse>. Accessed July 18, 2023.
- Kennedy, H. (2001). Conflict resolution and human rights: Contradictory or complementary? *INCORE*. <https://www.beyondintractability.org/bi-essay/human-rights-violation>. Retrieved July 17, 2023.
- Langford, M., Oslo, A., and Yamin, A. E. (2013). *The Millennium Development Goals and Human Rights*. Cambridge University Press.
- Maiese, M. (2003). Human Rights Violations: What it means to violate human rights. <https://www.beyondintractability.org/human-rights>. Retrieved April 15, 2023.
- Moyn, S. (2010). *The Last Utopia: Human Rights in History*. Harvard University Press.
- Nickel, J. (2021). Human rights. E. N. Zatta (ed). *The Standard Encyclopedia of Philosophy*. <https://www.plato.standard.edu/archives/fall2021/entries/rights-human>. Retrieved May 20, 2023.
- Nwangwu, C. (2022). Neo-Biafra separatist agitation, state repression, and insecurity in southeast, Nigeria. *Society*. 60 (4), 1-14.

- Nwanguma, O. (2013). Anambra State: Rule of law and constitutionalism under assault: Human rights in retreat. *Sahara Reporters*. <https://www.sharareporters.com/2013/08/18/anambra-state-rule-of-law-and-constitutionalism-under-assault-human-rights-retreat-okechukwu>. Retrieved October 15, 2023.
- Nzarga, F.D. (2014). An analysis of human rights violations by the Nigerian security services. *Journal of Law, Policy and Globalization*. Vol. 30, 56-64.
- Obaji, P. (2020). Women abused by police enforcing COVID-19 rules in Nigeria. <https://www.adjazeera.com>. Retrieved October 19, 2023.
- Okin, S. (1998). Feminism, women's human rights, and cultural difference. *Hypatia*. 13, 32-52.
- Paust, J. J. et al. (2001). *Human Rights Module: On Crimes against Humanity, Genocide, and Other Crimes against Human Rights and War Crimes*. Carolina Academic Press.
- Sahara Reporters. (2020). Police arrest officer who raped women apprehended for not wearing a face mask. <https://www.saharareporters.com/2020/07/31/police-arrest-officer-who-raped-women-apprehended-for-not-wearing-face-mask>. Retrieved December 10, 2023.
- Schwie, H. (2023). Examples of human rights violations: The borgen project. <https://www.borgenproject.org>. Retrieved August 15, 2023.
- The Federal Republic of Nigeria. *The 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria*. Federal Government Press.
- The Port City News. (2020). Breaking: Rivers police arraign Sergeant Bitrus Osaiah in court for killing female colleague. <https://www.theportcitynews.com/2020/04/28biturs-osaiah>. Retrieved October 21, 2023.
- Ukpong, C. (2021). Gunmen attack police patrol, kill officer in Anambra. *Premium Times*. <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/regional/ssouth-east/449858-breaking-gunmen-attack-police-patrol-kill-officer-in-anambra.html>. Retrieved November 10, 2023.
- United Nations General Assembly. (1948). Universal declaration of human rights. <https://www.un.org/about-us/universal-declaration-of-human-rights>. Retrieved August 11, 2023.
- United Nations. (2000). Human rights today: A United Nations' priority. <https://www.un.org/rights/HRT.daw>. Accessed 11 May 2023.
- United Nations. (2021). Sexual violence and armed conflict: United Nations' response. <https://www.un.org/womenwatch/daw/public/cover.htm>. Retrieved July 15, 2023.
- United Nations: Equality and Human Rights Commission. (2023). What are human rights? <https://www.equalityhumanrights.com/en/human-rights/what-are-human-rights>. Accessed 15 June 2023.
- Weston, B. H. (2023). *Encyclopedia Britannica*. <https://www.britannica.com/human-rights>. Retrieved May 16, 2023.
- Yusuf, K. (2021). Timeline: 10 police officers killed, six stations razed in two weeks. *Premium Times*. <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/headlines/449892-timeline-10->

[police-officers-killed-six-stations-](#)

[razed-in-two-weeks.html.](#)

Retrieved November 10, 2023.